

Framework of Material Considerations in Architectural Design: The interaction between context, manufacturing, experience and material aspects

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Abstract

Material selection in architecture is not always based on conscious and well-considered decisions. This paper aims to get a better insight in the aspects that contribute to these decisions taken during the material selection process. A focus group study and in-depth interviews allowed to identify ‘context’, ‘manufacturing process’, ‘experience’, and ‘material aspects’ as the elements that are considered by architects when selecting materials. In this paper, the interaction between the different aspects is investigated and discussed. The context will create a set of preconditions to start from or to frame and guide decisions in the other fields. Aspects concerning the experience, manufacturing process, and the material behavior, will interact and influence each other and will be considered based on the given context. In order to make justifiable material choices, the architect will run through all four considerations before making a final material decision.

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I. Introduction

Architects do not only design for function and use but also for experience. The materials that shape an environment will largely influence the user’s perception of that environment. Choosing materials for an architecture project is not only about meeting technical requirements, the material’s appearance and sensory interaction play an equally important role while designing (Ashby, Johnson, 2002) (Fernandez, 2006) (Pallasmaa, 2005) (Malnar, Vodvarka, 2004).

Within the field of product design, several research studies focus on product experiences. (Desmet, Hekkert, 2007) Within these product experiences a distinction can be made between the sensory experience, the attribution of meaning, and the generation of emotions. (Desmet, 2003) (Hekkert, 2006) (Schifferstein, Cleiren, 2005) (Schifferstein, Hekkert, 2007) More specifically towards materials, the product personally is researched in relation to the materials (van Kesteren, 2005). Karana and van Kesteren (2006) developed a 'material experiences evaluation model' which expresses the parameters of interaction between materials and people. They also state that people evaluate a product, not only based on the physical characteristics but also on sensorial or perceptive characteristics of the materials.

In architecture, little is known about the impact of material aspects on the overall experience of a project or space. Even though architects reason in terms of the atmosphere or experience they want to create and the attributes they need to create this experience (Wastiels, Wouters, Lindekens, 2007), the current information tools and material databases only provide information on the technical performance of materials. An increasing amount of books attributes attention to the intangible aspects of materials (Addington, Schodek, 2005) (Beylerian, Dent, Moryadas, 2005) (Keuning et al, 2004) but this interest is limited to an occasional description of the phenomena without providing a clear and comprehensive overview that might be useful to architect-designers.

In order to get a better view of the information on materials that might be useful to architects, it is important to understand the material selection process into more detail. This paper investigates this material selection process in architecture and organizes the different aspects considered into a workable framework. Integrating this information in a framework will ease communication on materials and the decisions taken, and helps in clarifying the relation between different decisions. Gaining a better insight in this process and the different aspects that are considered, will help in determining what material information might be useful for architects while selecting materials.

Focus group

A previous study, where in-depth interviews with architects were analyzed (Wastiels, Wouters, Lindekens, 2007), illustrated the complexity of the material selection process and determined the vocabulary used by architects to describe materials. For this paper, a focus group test with five professional architects was conducted in order to improve and refine the earlier developed framework (Wastiels, Wouters, Lindekens, 2007) into a comprehensive overview of material selection considerations for architecture projects.

Participants. Five subjects, three male and two female Belgian architects, between 23 and 46 years of age (average age 39), participated in the group discussion. All of them work in practice and their professional experience varies between 6 months and 20 years, with an average of 15 years. They were not informed on the subject of the discussion.

Procedure. The focus group study consisted of three phases. First, participants were asked to individually list the aspects they consider while selecting a material for a project. They were given some examples of specific material selection cases, extracted from interviews in a previous study. These extracts covered a variety of aspects, ranging from function to technical aspects, but were kept minimal in order not to influence or limit their thoughts. Words were written down for 20 minutes on separate post-it notes. Subsequently, the respondents were requested to perform a free classification task, categorize all notes and ascribe matching headings. They were invited to organize the aspects into groups in any way that seemed reasonable to them, without any constraints on the number or size of classes. A final categorization was established after about one hour. The complete discussion was videotaped for further reference during the analysis. To end, after a short break, the earlier framework was presented by the researcher and the respondents were asked to compare and discuss the two frameworks.

Analysis

The first step was to identify the different elements at play while selecting a material in a building context. These elements are described in the following section. An elaborate description of the process and methods used to retrieve these categories, as well as the discussion of the elements suggested by the focus group can be found in (Wastiels, Wouters, 2008).

The second step was to combine the elements based on their interaction and present a model that shows the interactions of material selection considerations. Once the elements were identified, the focus group discussion was evaluated for the interaction between the different considerations. The transcripts of both the focus group study and the interviews (Wastiels, Wouters, Lindekens, 2007) were analyzed for the lines of thought (Lawson, 1994) (Lindekens, Heylighen, 2008) in material decisions. Within these lines of thought, the meaning of the different considerations was evaluated in reference to each other. A refined model of considerations concerning materials in architecture including the interactions between the elements is presented as a result.

II. Material selection considerations

Four general elements have been identified as influencing the architect's material choice: Context [C], Manufacturing process [P], Experience [X], and Material aspects [M]. Each element can be subdivided into different groups that describe those considerations more specifically (Fig 1). Before elaborating on the interaction between the groups, a short description of the elements follows.

Figure 1: Four major elements considered while selecting materials in architecture.

Context

[C1] [physical context] When selecting materials, architects evaluate the project location (orientation, accessibility) and the immediate environment (adjacent materials and buildings). The physical location usually creates a first set of preconditions for the design choices.

[C2] [context of use] Architects investigate the context in which the material is applied (interior/exterior, renovation/newly built) or the function the material will have to accommodate (building's use, building element). The character of the project determines the materialization: a kindergarten, a city hall, or a hospital each require a different kind of materialization.

[C3] [cultural context] All considerations that concern cultural values (ethics, style, ecology) define the cultural context and impact the material choice. Also the interaction between time, money and ethics relates to the culture.

Manufacturing process

[P1] [production process] Molding, casting, bulk forming, sheet forming, lay-up methods and rapid prototyping are a number of broad families of production processes that might impact the material considerations. (Ashby, Johnson, 2002)

[P2] [assembly] The number of components, ease of assembly, and joining process all influence the manufacture of a building and thus also the material choice.

[P3] [finishing process] Surface modifications, such as printing, polishing, coating, or texturing, might enhance the thermal, friction, or aesthetic qualities while leaving the bulk properties unchanged. (Ashby, Johnson, 2002) Not all finishes can be applied to all materials.

Experiences

[X1] [perception] Architects might consider materials based on the intended atmosphere for a project. When being asked to design a hard volume, or a friendly space, each designer will compose a different palette of materials which he believes will contribute in creating the intended expression.

[X2] [association] Associative meanings are fed by the associations people make with aspects, objects or situations they know (hospital-like, cheap-looking, Swiss-cabin material). Architects can employ these meanings while choosing materials.

[X3] [emotion] The surroundings will affect people's emotions, and architects might have the intention to move people through their architecture. A particular spatial composition, in combination with specific lighting, and well-chosen materials might evoke personal emotional reactions (beautiful, repulsive, pleasant) with its occupants.

Material aspects

[M1] [physical aspects] In order to meet certain performance aspects, architects consider the material's technical aspects, like stiffness, strength, porosity, density, or thermal absorption coefficient.

[M2] [sensorial aspects] The appearance, or more generally the sensorial behavior, of materials creates a field of opportunities for architects selecting materials. It is largely through these characteristics that the architect keeps control over how the building will look and feel like and that he will provide an answer to the desired or intended expression and appearance of the project.

III. Interactions between the considered categories

In the presented framework, no pronouncement is made upon how considerations from these different categories influence each other. From the different examples available from the focus group study, as well as from in-depth interviews (Wastiels, Wouters, Lindekens, 2007), however, it becomes clear that most considerations will interact or influence each other, and that the selection of a material is based on considerations from all groups rather than one.

Context as a set of preconditions

A distinction can be made between elements that relate to a specific material decision and elements that describe or define the set of preconditions for selection. In this matter, the reflections concerning the context are different from the other elements in the framework. The

manufacturing process, *material aspects*, and *experience* represent the aspects the architect can take decisions in. The *context* considerations describe the aspects that are defined by the project situation, and thus correspond to the set of preconditions the architect has to take into account while taking decisions.

Because the contextual considerations characterize a set of preconditions, they will influence or guide the considerations and further decisions. A one-way interaction can be defined between aspects from the context group (physical, use, or cultural) and the other groups (Fig. 2).

Examples retrieved from the focus group study, illustrate this interaction with the [*manufacturing process*], [*material aspects*] and [*experience*]. They also show that, even though the context is a given, each designer will select other aspects from that context to guide or verify his material decisions.

context → *manufacturing process*: When building in the woods [*context*], the construction site might be difficult to access by truck. For practical reasons, this precondition might exclude the possibility of casting concrete on site from the design options [*manufacturing process*].

context → *material aspects*: The function or use specified for a room or building, can demand a specific performance from the materials applied. When choosing materials for a bathroom [*context*], material aspects such as ‘water-repellent’, ‘non-porous’, and ‘slip-resistant’ [*material aspects*] will guide the material selection process.

context → *experience*: Selecting materials for a renovation project might be influenced by the atmosphere in the existing project [*context*]. In response to the cold and formal materials that are present in a project, the architect might choose to create a warm and friendly space [*experience*].

Figure 2: Relation between the different elements considered while selecting materials. The context influences the other three elements, which are interacting interdependent.

Even though only some specific examples of interaction are provided here, each aspect considered concerning the context (physical, use, or cultural) formulates a set of preconditions that will influence any of the other considerations made for material selection (including all subgroups represented in Fig. 1). The preconditions will help, guide and limit the designer while taking decisions. Reversely, the decisions will not influence or determine the context, but will

be defined by it. One can not alter the existing context but only interpret it. This relationship is represented in figure 2 by a one-way arrow.

Interactions between decisions

The focus group discussion and in-depth interviews reveal that during the search for a material, all four categories will have to be thought over before taking a final decision on a material. As one of the architects mentions during the focus group discussion: *“You can not dictate a material to a building. It demands its own material, from a certain logic, and from a set of preconditions, which can be contextual but also emerge from the design. And it is together that they receive their meaning”*. Besides the determining influence of the context, an internal interaction exists between the different considerations where the designer has to take a decision in. Moreover, decisions taken for one aspect will impact the options left for the other aspects. For example, when considering a desired project experience, the architect will draw on specific materials or material aspects to create this experience. These material aspects will in turn require specific manufacturing techniques in order to be achieved. Below, we discuss some real material selection processes extracted from the interviews in order to illustrate this interaction between the different elements.

experience → *material aspects* → *manufacturing process*: For the design of an extension to a law school, the architect ended up with colored plaster for the interior walls of the lobby. Because the existing space [*context*] was very cold and unfriendly, the architect wanted to create a warm space [*experience*]. Looking for a warm material [*material aspects*], wood was considered to be used. However, problems occurring for the detailing and assembly of the wood paneling [*manufacturing process*] forced the designer to look for alternatives. Colored plaster [*material aspects*] seemed suitable to be applied [*manufacturing process*] while also providing an answer to the desired warmth [*experience*] through its color.

manufacturing process → *experience* → *material aspects*: For a project to be built along the New England coast, cedar clapboard facing was used to cover the façade. The architects were forced to design according to the vernacular architecture [*context*] because of the contractor’s limited capabilities [*context*]. This resulted in the use of clapboard [*manufacturing process*] which is typical for New England. Starting from the clapboard system, the architects wanted an expression that was different from the formal and rigorous brick buildings in the surroundings [*experience*] and chose to go for wooden slats. In order to meet the technical requirements the wood should be resistant to the decomposition of moisture and insects [*material aspects*], so they decided to use red cedar.

material aspects → *manufacturing process* → *experience*: In the main entrance hall for a university building, a large brushed stainless steel wall invites the visitors into the building. Because people would lean against and skim along the wall [*context*], the architect chose to use steel because it is resistant to indentations and does not get dirty [*material aspects*]. The connections between the clean lined panels were simple reveals [*manufacturing process*] so the feeling was that you entered a formal but progressive place [*experience*]. In order to keep the overall quality of warmth for the space [*experience*], the stainless steel was brushed [*manufacturing process*] which gives a texture and a sort of depth to the material [*material aspects*].

The examples illustrate that the different decisions concerning the material influence each other and that the reasoning process can start from the experience, the manufacturing process, as well as the material aspects. Depending on the situation (context) as well as the design spirit of the architect, a different decision will take the lead. In general, the more technical decisions and proposals are initiated from the material properties, where the more conceptual decisions tend to emerge from the experience.

IV. Conclusion and discussion

Conclusion

‘Context’, ‘Manufacturing process’, ‘Material aspects’, and ‘Experience’ are all identified as aspects that influence and determine the material selection process. A framework representing these elements and their mutual interactions has been developed and presented here.

In general we can state that an architect makes considerations about the existing situation, being the context, which he interprets as a set of preconditions to work with and provide an answer to. Next to this, material decisions are made based on several elements that the designer controls himself: manufacturing process, material performance, and project experience. These elements are defined by the designer during the design process. Taking decisions for any of these considerations will influence the room left for the other elements to vary.

Limited material vocabulary

The analysis of the interviews conducted earlier, as well as of the focus group study, suggests that architects think according to all the aspects of the framework but maybe only consciously use part of it. Even though all aspects of the framework are considered during the material selection process, some of the thoughts or reflections seem to be made intuitively or unconsciously. For example, during the focus group discussion, the production process was not

mentioned as an influencing parameter for material selection. During the reflective discussion afterwards, however, all participants agreed that the production process has an impact on the material decisions. Someone mentioned as an example that a mold would not be fabricated if it were for an element only to be used once throughout the construction process. The consideration of the production process seemed so obvious that it slipped their mind while constructing the framework.

On the other hand, several quotes from the study illustrate that a large number of mental leaps are made while speaking about selecting a material or designing in general. One participant mentioned that “one will not construct a bunker out of glass”. A number of considerations and meanings are hidden within this statement which reveals the interaction between several considerations, but also implies certain implicit meanings that are not made explicit during the material selection process. (1) Functionally, one should be invisible to the enemy – so no transparent material. (2) In terms of material performance, the material has to withstand mechanical shocks from attacks – so no brittle material. (3) In terms of experience a bunker is perceived to be robust – so no glass because it is associated with lightness and fragileness.

Untangling the process of material selection helps to understand the mechanism at play and leads to a better understanding of why certain decisions are made. The bunker (not) made out of glass seems obvious to anyone hearing it, because thinking of only one of the mental leaps is sufficient to clarify the choice. Gaining a better insight in all the aspects at play, however, can contribute in making more conscious material decisions or finding valuable alternatives. In order to gain insight in a larger range of materials possibilities and solutions, we believe it is important to utilize all the elements of the framework in a more conscious way.

Exploring the framework

Part of the reason for the mental leaps, or the unconscious decisions, might be found in the level of subjectivity of some of the aspects. During the focus group discussion, the participants define and describe the technical material parameters unambiguously. They refer to them as engineering parameters and argue that everybody utilizes the same definition for aspects such as hardness, stiffness, or porosity of a material. For the sensorial properties the descriptions are sometimes less objective. Visual aspects such as gloss or transparency do not pose a problem, but less obvious tactile aspects such as softness or warmth initiate discussions at a certain point.

Especially for the experience aspects, the participants are being faced with difficulties when describing what they mean and discussions arise because of the lack of definition or knowledge about them. The initial name the focus groups chose for the experience group, ‘intuitive’, illustrates that these aspects seem obvious and intuitive to them without being able to explain

them. The distinction made between perception, association and emotion is presented here by the author, based on a literature study. Based on the results from the focus groups study, it seems that architects do not make a distinction between these aspects while designing.

Going back to the framework we distinguish the shift in the level of objectivity for the decisions to be made, ranging from most objective for manufacturing processes to most subjective for experiences. In order to get architects consciously involved in the material selection process, materials should be described into as much detail as possible. Based on the decision elements represented in the framework one could present a model of desired material information for architects, with information going from very objective technical information to most subjective emotive descriptions. For the most subjective descriptions (emotions and associations), it will be hard to formulate definitions for the different aspects. However, for the less abstract aspects (sensorial descriptions, and even perceptions) we believe a quantifiable description can be provided that allows architects to make more considerate material choices. A description of the intangible aspects of materials important to architects and designers can facilitate their material selection process and might be a good start for bridging the gap between architects and engineers/material scientists.

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References

- Addington, M. and Schodek, D.L. (2005). "Smart materials and Technologies in Architecture." Oxford: Architectural Press.
- Ashby, M.F. and Johnson, K. (2002). "Materials and Design: The Art and Science of Material Selection in Product Design." Oxford; Boston: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Beylerian, G.M., Dent, A. and Moryadas, A. (ed.) (2005). "Material ConneXion: The Global Resource of New and Innovative Materials for Architects, Artists and Designers." Hoboken, N.J.: Wiley.
- Desmet, P.M.A. (2003). "A multilayered model of product emotions." *The Design Journal*, 6 (2), 4-13
- Desmet, P.M.A. and Hekkert, P. (2007). "Framework of Product Experience." *International Journal of Design*, 1 (1), 57-66
- Fernandez, J.E. (2006). "Material Architecture: Emergent materials for innovative buildings and ecological construction." Amsterdam; Boston: Architectural Press.
- Hekkert, P. (2006). "Design aesthetics: principles of pleasure in design." *Psychology Science*, 48, 157-172

- Karana, E. and van Kesteren, I.E.H. (2006). "Material effects: the role of materials in people's product evaluations." Design and Emotion Conference 2006, Göteborg, Sweden, September 27-29
- Keuning, D., Melet, E., Kruit, C., Peterse, K., Vollaard, P., de Vries, T. and Zijlstra, E. (2004). "Skins For Buildings: The architect's materials sample book." Amsterdam: BIS
- Lawson, B. (1994) "Design in Mind." Oxford: Butterworth Architecture.
- Lindekens, J. and Heylighen, A. (2008). "Chunks, lines and strategies. A three-component representation to capture and exchange architects' design processes." AIEDAM Special Issue, 22(4).
- Malnar, J.M. and Vodvarka, F. (2004). "Sensory Design." University of Minnesota Press.
- Pallasmaa, J. (2005). "The Eyes of the Skin: Architecture and the Senses." (2nd ed.) Academy Press.
- Schifferstein, H.N.J. and Cleiren, M.P.H.D (2005). "Capturing product experiences: a split-modality approach." Acta Psychologica, 118, 293-318.
- Schifferstein, H.N.J. and Hekkert, P. (2007). "Product Experience." Elsevier.
- van Kesteren, I.E.H., Stappers, P.J. and Kandachar, P.V. (2005). "Representing product personality in relation to materials in a product design problem." Nordic Design Research Conference, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2005
- Wastiels, L., Wouters, I. and Lindekens, J. (2007) "Material Knowledge for Design: The architect's vocabulary." International Association of Societies of Design Research (IASDR) Conference, Hong Kong, Hong Kong, November 11-15
- Wastiels, L. and Wouters, I. (2008) "Material Considerations in Architectural Design: A study of the aspects identified by architects for selecting materials." Undisciplined! Design Research Society (DRS) Conference, Sheffield, UK, July 16-19